

Sample 24a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0011
	{Si}	45.3
	{Cl}	7.9
	{Cl}	5.6
	{Al, Si}	4.6
	{Ca}	3.5
	{S, Ca}	3.5
	{Fe}	3.5
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.4
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.6
	{Al, Si, K}	2.0
	{Si, Cl}	1.5
	{Si, Ca HIP}	1.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.3
	{Mg, Ca}	1.1
	{Al, Cl}	1.1
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.8
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Na, Si}	0.8
	{Al}	0.7
	{Si, Fe}	0.6
	{Zn-LA1}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Ti}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.6
Pellet	0.4
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.9
BOF converter slag	0.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.1
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.9
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.1
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	4.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.5
Carbon rich - other	20.1
Cement or BOF converter	0.7
Cement	4.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	1.6
Ti-rich paint	0.8
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	1.0
Salt or salt layer	0.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	43.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	12.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.4
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.7
Site - ore / hot metal	0.9
Site - slag	3.3
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.9
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.2
Site - flux / slag	0.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.3
Site - carbon-rich other	1.5
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	20.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.7
Urban	7.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.5
Natural mineral background	43.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	12.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.3
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.4

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 24b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0014
	{Si}	40.3
	{Cl}	7.5
	{Cl}	5.8
	{Al, Si}	4.8
	{Ca}	4.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.9
	{Fe}	3.1
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.1
	{S, Ca}	3.1
	{Al, Si, K}	2.4
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.1
	{Al, Cl}	2.0
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.8
	{Si, Cl}	1.7
	{Al}	1.4
	{Si, Ca HIP}	1.0
	{Na, Si}	1.0
	{Zn-LA1}	0.9
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.8
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Ca}	0.6
	{S}	0.5
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, Fe}	0.4
	{Cl, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Cl}	0.4
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, S, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Cl}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	0.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	0.9
BOF converter slag slopping	1.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	3.0
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.9
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	6.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.0
Carbon rich - other	16.8
Cement or BOF converter	0.3
Cement	1.6
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.3
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	3.7
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	45.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	1.5
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.5
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	2.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	6.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	2.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.9
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.5
Site - carbon-rich other	1.0
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	16.8
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.3
Urban	5.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	45.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	1.5
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 24c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0010
	{Si}	38.7
	{Cl}	8.7
	{Cl}	6.6
	{Al, Si}	5.5
	{Ca}	5.5
	{Fe}	4.0
	{Al, Si, K}	3.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.7
	{S, Ca}	2.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.3
	{Si, Ca HIP}	1.4
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.4
	{Al, Cl}	1.3
	{Si, Cl}	1.3
	{Na, Si}	1.2
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	1.0
	{Al}	1.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Ca}	0.6
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.6
	{Si, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Cl}	0.4
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Zn-LA1}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Na, S, Cl, Ca}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.0
Pellet	0.4
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.5
BOF converter slag	0.6
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.9
Desulph slag	2.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.9
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	3.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.9
Carbon rich - other	19.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.1
Cement	2.9
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	2.1
Salt or salt layer	1.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	40.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	11.8
Misc silicates including natural	0.4
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.4
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	3.1
Site - ore / hot metal	0.5
Site - slag	5.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.2
Site - flux / slag	2.9
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.6
Site - carbon-rich other	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	19.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.1
Urban	5.7
Natural salt - immediate	1.8
Natural mineral background	40.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	11.8
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.6
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.6

141 μm

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels